

Making Citizens' systems more Secure: Practical Encryption Bypassing and Countermeasures

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Abstract— *Cryptography is used to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of information by preventing unauthorized users from accessing or modifying them. Encryption techniques are used to protect personal or company data. This work demonstrates practical scenarios where, under certain conditions, encryption may be bypassed. Bypassing encryption, either by recovering the encryption key, a password used to generate the encryption key, or a plaintext copy of the encrypted data, allows for accessing data which appear to be inaccessible in the first place. There are six categories for bypassing encryption: find the key, guess the key, compel the key, exploit a flaw in the encryption scheme, access unencrypted message when the device is in use and locate an unencrypted copy of the message. In this study we utilize publicly available software to demonstrate real-world scenarios that fall into most of the aforementioned categories and show how, in those specific cases, encryption may be successfully bypassed. Moreover, we underline that bypassing encryption is possible only when certain conditions are met (e.g., software misconfiguration, physical access to the target device, etc.) and we highlight each one of them so as to effectively suggest countermeasures to the demonstrated techniques for encryption bypassing. The main aim of this paper is to highlight how encryption can be bypassed and thus make citizens set up their system in such a way that it would be more difficult to be hacked. This is especially important for citizens that may have limited knowledge/exposure to technology as they can be, for example, people from certain diversity groups such as elderly and/or people of very low income.*

Keywords—*encryption, hacking, protection*

I. INTRODUCTION

In contemporary society encryption has become an essential feature of everyday life for digital communication and storage. Everyone who uses a smartphone, or a computer utilizes cryptography, maybe without even realizing it. Encryption plays a key role in the protecting of user's data by preventing unauthorized users from accessing them. In addition, it is used to confirm the integrity and authenticity of data.

Encryption transforms data to an unintelligible form, which is known as ciphertext, using an encryption algorithm and an encryption key. According to Kerckhoffs' principle "the security of the encryption scheme must depend only on the secrecy of the encryption key, and not on the secrecy of the algorithm.". So ciphertext can be returned to readable format (known as plaintext) only in the case the decryption key is known. The decryption key can be the same as the encryption key in the case of symmetric encryption (secret key) and different in the case of asymmetric encryption (public key).

In addition to an encryption algorithm there is also a hash function employed in cryptography schemes. The hash function makes data unintelligible; the difference when comparing it to encryption is that hash is a one-way function, and the data cannot be returned in the original form again. Hash functions convert data of arbitrary length to a fixed length. If two messages are identical, their hashes are also identical, so, in order to find the message given the hash, different hashed messages must be tested until the same hash is found.

Fig 1 Encryption scheme

Fig 2 Hash process

Unfortunately, encryption and/or hashing can be hacked/bypassed and in this case the user data can be read by unauthorized, and very often, malicious hackers. In this way a hacker can get, for example access to the bank details/accounts of the users or to private and/or sensitive information. It has been proved that the less technology literate a person is the easiest he/she is to be hacked [1]. Moreover, people for certain diversity groups such as the elderly, people from ethnical minorities or low-income citizens are more likely to be less technology literate than a middle-class citizen thus it is even more important for them to highlight how their encrypted data can be hacked and how they can protect them.

The definition "encryption workaround" along with general methods for its implementation are reported in [1],[2],[3] [4]. With the term encryption workaround, we mean any method in which an unencrypted version of the user's data can be identified and read/collected, either by disclosing the encryption key or by disclosing a copy of the data. The general categories along with the methods applied in each

category of encryption workaround are depicted on the table below:

TABLE 1 Categories of encryption workaround

Category	Methods
Find the key: find an existing copy of the key. All passwords, passcodes, and passphrases can treat as key	<p>File Search: Key is written into a file of computer/phone</p> <p>Modern Browsers: passwords saved in browsers</p> <p>Encryption Program: program leaves the key in memory/file</p> <p>Forensic analysis: keys stored in a computer somewhere</p> <p>Encryption software: Key in a single file which is encrypted</p> <p>Password manager: keys encrypted with the master password of password manager and saved by password manager</p> <p>Keylogger: keylogger logs the password when user enter it using the computer.</p>
Guess the key: a passcode/password can be relatively easy to guess. And since password unlocks the encryption key, guessing the password has the same effect as guessing the encryption key.	<p>Guess a password with limitations (e.g., only numbers): some systems have limitations on what sort of password can be used</p> <p>Guess without any limitation: password with arbitrary length and any typable character</p> <p>Educated guesses: guesses about what user is likely to have used</p> <p>Guess with Wordlist: try the most used passwords from users</p> <p>Guess with Brute Force: (i) offline: the encrypted file removed. Millions of tries per second (ii) online: on the seized device with limitations by manufacturers</p>
Compel the key: based on laws. Compel the key from someone who has or know it	Based on Laws
Exploit a flaw in the Encryption Scheme: exploit a flaw to gain access without key	<p>Weakness in the encryption scheme: vulnerability on software like mathematical weakness etc. or a mistake by system designer.</p> <p>Backdoor: flaw that is deliberately inserted to subvert the system security</p> <p>Exploit a flaw: find a vulnerability on the system</p>
Access plaintext when the device is in use: intended users cannot read ciphertext, so encrypted data must be decrypted to be readable	<p>have ongoing access to the device in use: access the device will enable access to unencrypted information</p> <p>use keylogger with hidden camera: keylogger collect keystrokes typed by the user, passwords etc. and camera spies what the user sees on computer.</p> <p>Remote access: "hack" into the device remotely while it is connected to the internet. The remote connection provides access to the computer without physical access</p> <p>Installing Malware: install a malware on the device of user to gain access on it.</p>
Locate a plaintext copy: obtain a separate and unencrypted copy of the information.	<p>Find earlier drafts of a file: find unencrypted earlier drafts from the file that the word processing software had automatically created.</p> <p>Find information (file, e-mail) on cloud provider: find copies of the file that is stored in the cloud.</p>

Thus, in this work we demonstrate practical scenarios that fall into all the above mentioned categories and in which we demonstrate that there are real-world ways to bypass encryption. The rest of this work is organized as follows: Initially, we present scenarios for (a) encryption key recovery from RAM for commonly used disk encryption software (VeraCrypt, BitLocker on Windows 10), (b) for

encrypted password recovery from web browser password stores (Chrome, Firefox on Windows 10), (c) for key and password recovery stored in documents through advanced search utilizing regular expressions (Windows 10) and (d) for recovery of unencrypted copies of deleted data (Windows 10). (e) The conclusions and future work are presented.

II. FIND THE KEY: KEY RECOVERY FROM RAM

A. Implementation and Prerequisites of VeraCrypt

Implementation (VeraCrypt): In the case the user utilizes VeraCrypt for hard disk encryption we analyze an attack, without any loss in generality, when Veracrypt is configured with one master 512-bit key constructed by two 256-bit keys from the same encryption algorithms which is AES (i.e. the default). For the attack we used the aeskeyfind tool [8] which locates 128 and 256-bit AES encryption keys on a memory image. We saved every 256-bit key in a file. Then, knowing that VeraCrypt uses a master key of 512 bit, we tested every possible combination of two 256-bit keys to mount the encrypted flash drive, with MKDecrypt [9] tool, until we successfully mount the disk. In more details, in order to do so we developed a python-script for creating the 512-bit keys and a bash-script for trying to mount the hard-disk using the generated 512-bit key, until we successfully mount it (i.e. find the correct key as in Figure 3).

Prerequisites (VeraCrypt): The prerequisites for effectively applying the listed encryption bypassing technique are: (a) Ability to acquire a RAM dump while the encrypted volume/drive is mounted. This can be achieved with physical access to the computer or by applying a cold boot attack, using a device with Direct Memory Access like PCILeech [10] while the computer is locked, or using a HID device (like rubber ducky) as part of a malware executed on the computer. (b) The user has chosen the default option (i.e. AES) for the "encryption algorithm" in VeraCrypt. (c) The user has chosen the default option (i.e. NO) for "encrypt the encryption keys in RAM". (d) Physical access to the encrypted drive.

B. Implementation and Prerequisites of BitLocker

Implementation (BitLocker): In the case the citizen uses BitLocker we identify the potential keys in the memory dump of RAM, with Volatility [11] and BitLocker-Volatility plugins [12] which both store every potential key in a .fvek file. Then, by using a bash-script we developed, we test every key listed using the dislocker [13] tool, to mount the encrypted flash drive until we successfully mount the disk, as in Figure 4. With this approach, we got the correct master-key. Moreover, because BitLocker also uses the AES algorithm for encryption, the approach we followed in VeraCrypt, can also be applied to BitLocker as well.

Prerequisites (BitLocker): The prerequisites for effectively applying the listed encryption bypassing technique are two only: (a) Ability to acquire a memory dump while the encrypted flash drive is mounted and (b) physical access to the encrypted flash drive is required.

46af7cc6a1dd3f18facc2ce26e498514258c675dcc304cd88526640e4f4141d
ef0950336e3d1171e8fbf2fd20355a52dc9e409cf340fe932911e9850d2bcab2

Fig 3 VeraCrypt encryption key recovered from RAM master_key.txt

```

[syrgiann@kali] ~/Desktop
└─$ sudo sh ./trying_every_fvek_key_to_mount_bitlocker.sh ~/Desktop/bitlockerkeys /dev/sdb ~/Desktop/BitLocker
mount: /home/syrgiann/Desktop/BitLocker: wrong fs type, bad option, bad superblock on /dev/loop0, missing codep
age or helper program, or other error.
This key isn't correct: /home/syrgiann/Desktop/bitlockerkeys/0x818503b5faa0-Dislocker.fvek
The correct key is:
/home/syrgiann/Desktop/bitlockerkeys/0x81850c8f2a20-Dislocker.fvek
Mounted on /home/syrgiann/Desktop/BitLocker

```

Fig 4 BitLocker encryption keys recovered from RAM trying to mount encrypted drive

C. Lessons learned and Countermeasures

Lessons learned: The techniques described in the last section lead us to the conclusion that finding the encryption keys in RAM is not easy since. (a) It is quite difficult to obtain a snapshot of the RAM when you have not access to the computer, (b) It is essential to acquire the RAM dump while the encrypted drive is in use (mounted), (c) Physical access to the encrypted drive is required, (d) It is only for the AES keys that there exists a tool that can find them in a memory image, otherwise keys can only be found if the method of storing them in RAM, by the disk encryption software, is known and (e) If a memory dump when the encrypted drive is mounted, falls into the attacker's hand there is nothing the user can further do to save his/her data.

Countermeasures: In order to defend against those encryption bypassing techniques users should (a) avoid selecting the AES algorithm when using a disk encryption software and instead use a more advanced encryption algorithm, (b) if the disk encryption software allows the encryption of the keys stored in RAM, the user should select it and (c) the implementation only works for encryption software that uses OTFE, so by choosing a different disk encryption software, which follows another approach for encryption, the listed bypassing techniques are ineffective.

III. GUESS THE KEY: PASSWORD RECOVERY FROM BROWSERS

Scenario: In this scenario, user stores his/her usernames and passwords on a web browser's (e.g. Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox) password database, so as to automatically connect to sites (i.e. without inserting usernames and passwords again). Web browsers encrypt the passwords with an encryption key. Specifically, Google Chrome encrypts stored passwords with AES and 256-bit keys and this in turn is encrypted through Microsoft's Data Protection API (DPAPI). Mozilla Firefox encrypts stored passwords with 3DES and an 168-bit master-key which is encrypted with a key produced by a password based key derivation (PBKDF2[14]). The input to PBKDF2 is a password set by the user if he has chosen to use "Primary Password", otherwise, the default option, is that it is empty. Users very often use the same passwords in many different domains and/or applications, so it is highly possible that some of the passwords stored in the browser's database are also being used as passwords to, for example, encrypt a hard drive. Moreover, the browser stored passwords can be used to access user's online cloud accounts.

```

[syrgiann@kali] ~/Desktop
└─$ john --format=NT --incremental ~/Desktop/crack.txt
Using default input encoding: UTF-8
Loaded 1 password hash (NT [MD4 256/256 AVX2 8x3])
Warning: no OpenMP support for this hash type, consider --fork=3
Press 'q' or Ctrl-C to abort, almost any other key for status
1992nik (syrgiann)
1g 0:00:05:44 DONE (2022-04-28 16:47) 0.002906g/s 13203Kp/s 13203Kc/s 13203Kc/s 1992no5.1992njm
Use the "--show --format=NT" options to display all of the cracked passwords reliably
Session completed

```

Fig 5 Recovered Windows 10 password

```

C:\Users\syrgi\Desktop>python chromePASS.py
Origin URL: https://www.linkedin.com/uas/login
Action URL: https://www.linkedin.com/checkpoint/lg/login-submit
Username: nikos@gmail.com
Password: 1998nikolaoSoMeGa$
Creation date: 2022-04-28 14:23:59.523616
Last Used: 2022-04-28 14:23:57.514037

```

Fig 6 Recovered stored passwords from Google Chrome

```

C:\Users\syrgi\Desktop>python firefox_decrypt.py
Select the Mozilla profile you wish to decrypt
1 -> Profiles/pr2o7och.NikosUser
2 -> Profiles/cpknqaj2.default
3 -> Profiles/jpmbkq79.default-release
1

Website: https://www.linkedin.com
Username: 'nikos254@gmail.com'
Password: 'xZ^B&vCLVwL-9t!S'

```

Fig 7 Recovered stored passwords from Mozilla Firefox

Workaround: Based on this technique, recovery of stored passwords on Web Browsers and Windows 10 is feasible in a relatively fast fashion.

Methods and tools: For this attack, we used chromePASS.py [15] to extract the encrypted stored passwords in Google Chrome as demonstrated in Figure 6. As for Mozilla Firefox, if the user has selected the default option (without "Primary Password") we can extract the password via the browser or with firefox_decrypt.py [16] as shown in Figure 7. In the case of "Primary Password", we developed a tool crack_firefox_primary_password.py to try cracking the "Primary Password" first using a conventional dictionary attack.

Implementation: As the computer is turned-on the recovery of Web browsers-stored password is feasible. As for Google Chrome, the encryption keys of DPAPI are available to user to decrypt the stored passwords. It should be noted that if someone tries to bypass the local login password of Windows 10 (in the case the computer is turned off), all files encrypted via DPAPI will automatically be deleted from the computer along with all the stored passwords in Google Chrome; this is due to the fact that the DPAPI encryption keys are directly associated with the local login password. In the case of Mozilla Firefox, if the user has not activated the "Primary Password" option the stored passwords of the browser are directly accessible. Otherwise, a crack of the "primary password" is required first using a brute force or dictionary attack.

Prerequisites to recover stored passwords stored in Web Browsers: The prerequisites for effectively applying the listed encryption bypassing technique are: (a) If the computer is turned off, it should be turned on first (see below "Crack a closed computer"), (b) In the case of Google Chrome, the password of Windows 10 should not have been bypassed, (c) Time constraints for brute-force/dictionary attack in the case of Mozilla Firefox if the user has selected the "Primary Password" option. For example, a strong password of at least 8 characters long, using the full range of character types (special character, uppercase, lowercase, number) which is not easily predictable nor one of the set passwords included in an attack dictionary, can be cracked in a matter of years (e.g. up to 7) by a processor that tries 1 million attempts per second, (d) Physical access to the computer.

Crack a turned-off Windows 10 Computer: If the hard disk isn't encrypted, booting of the computer is not locked via a password, OS is Windows 10 and the computer is locked via user's local password, two approaches can be followed: one is password crack, and the other is password bypass. For both approaches, Kali Linux Live image on a USB is required to boot the computer [17]. Regarding bypassing the password, using the chntpw tool [18], we should first process the SAM file to remove the user's local password and thus login into the computer as the specified user (as shown in Figure 5). On the other hand, in order to crack the NT hash [19] of the password, SAM and SYSTEM files are required. These files are located on "C:\Windows\System32\config". These files should be transferred on a Machine running Kali Linux for further analysis. The SYSTEM file contains a 128-bit AES encryption key which encrypts/decrypts the SAM file. With Impacket[20], we can extract the AES key from SYSTEM, decrypt SAM and extract the NT hash of the password. Then, with John the Ripper [21] we can crack the user's local password.

A. Lessons learned and Countermeasures

Lessons learned: The recovery of Web browser stored passwords is not very easy since: (a) The disk should not be encrypted (b) In cases where we have to crack a master password, only short passwords will be cracked in a reasonable time while systems prompt, and even force sometimes, users to choose a strong password by requiring a minimal length of characters and use of all character types (special, uppercase, lowercase, numbers).

Countermeasures: In order to make their systems less vulnerable against the described attacks the users: (a) should consider the encryption of their hard disks, so to provide maximum security for each file on the disk, since a password or PIN is required for the disk to be unlocked, (b) should use strong passwords with at least 8 characters long, including all character types (special, uppercase, lowercase, number), (c) should use an additional password where possible, so as to increase the security of their data (i.e use two form authentication).

IV. FIND THE KEY: PASSWORD SEARCH USING ADVANCED SEARCH

Scenario: In this scenario we search for passwords stored in files on a user's computer. Possible such files are conventional document files (e.g .txt, .docx, .xlsx, .pdf etc.) Users use the same passwords in different applications, so it is possible the listed passwords are used as passwords in encrypted hard disks or in the user's online cloud account(s).

Workaround: If there is access to the turned-on computer, it is possible to find files that have stored passwords.

Methods and tools: As long as the computer is accessible we followed two approaches, one utilizes File Explorer and the other the PasswordSearcher.py we developed which is an extension of the DumpsterDiver tool [22].

A. File Explorer Implementation and Prerequisites

File Explorer Implementation: In the case of searching for files through File Explorer, we searched some keywords that may be included in the title, file properties and file contents

of a file that may contain passwords. For this purpose, we developed a tool filesearch.py which creates the query for the file explorer with keywords that are contained in a .txt file (i.e. a Wordlist). File Explorer will search for the words in indexed and non-indexed files. Indexed files are indexed only by their file properties (name, attributes etc.) or by file properties and file contents. Thus, files that are indexed only with file properties, such as .txt files in default options, will not be internally searched (i.e. based on their contents). On a typical personal computer (PC), the Indexer indexes fewer than 30,000 items. On high-end computer (used by a highly computer literate user) the indexer might index up to 300,000 items. If the indexer indexes more than 400,000 items, then the actual windows search is slow while it is highly likely that the Indexer cannot handle more than 1M files. As the number of indexed items grows beyond 400,000 the index database grows considerably regardless of the size of those items. The size of the items also affects the size of the database. A database that contains either a few large files or a large number of smaller files can affect the performance of the Indexer. As an example, 100 MB of text files will need less than 10 MB in the index database; in our reference case we have 272,444 indexed items which require 1,48 GB of Indexer's database space. On the other hand the non-indexed files are searched with file properties and/or file contents, depending on what the attacker has chosen, but they are searched slower than indexed files. For example, in order to search for file contents in a .txt file, it is essential to reconstruct the indexer by selecting the .txt files to be indexed. This increases the actual attack time; in our experiment, shown in Figure 8, we need approximately 1 hour for reconstructing the indexer so as to index 1,729,845 files of all types (the first 272,444 were initially indexed), while also we need almost 200GB of database space.

Prerequisites to find a password using File Explorer: The prerequisites for effectively applying the listed encryption bypassing technique are: (a) the computer must be turned-on and (b) in some cases, the time needed is very high. The high time demands have mainly to do with the search in file contents of non-indexed files as well as when a reconstruction of the indexer is needed. Thus, a complete search of the user's computer may take up to a few hours depending on the number of files in the computer and the size of these files.

B. PasswordSearcher Implementation and Prerequisites

PasswordSearcher Implementation: As for the PasswordSearcher tool we developed, it searches for words in files which meet certain criteria. In more details the specified words : (a) have 3 out of 4 categories of typable characters (1 at least special character, uppercase, lowercase and number) and (b) should have a big score in passwordmeter[23] (a score of 0.1 corresponds to a trivial password (or just a common word) while a score of 1 corresponds to a very complex password). Moreover, this tool allows the attacker to exclude from the search certain file extensions such as .java, .py (which contain programming code which may, though trigger the above criteria due to the structure of code) etc. Additionally, the attacker can insert the range of word lengths that will be considered acceptable for possible password. In Figure 9 we

illustrate a scenario for searching passwords in .pdf, docx, .xlsx, .txt files utilizing our PasswordSearcher.

Prerequisites PasswordSearcher: The prerequisites for effectively applying the listed encryption bypassing technique are : (a) a computer must be turned on (b) the required time depends on the number of folder (and its subfolders) that are searched, the files contained in the folder and subfolders and the size of files. Our PasswordSearcher, in a typical case, is rather fast since the actual searching of, for example, a Documents folder containing 278 files and 67 folders (at a total data size of 304MB), without excluding any file type, needs approximately 18 seconds. Thus, a complete search, on a typical computer, may take up to a few hours depending on the number of files on the computer, but this can be minimized by excluding files that are most likely not to contain passwords such as files with extensions .java, .py, .c etc.

C. Lessons learned and Countermeasures

Lessons learned: To sum up : (a) if it is difficult/impossible to have access to a turned-on computer for several hours, this technique can be applied in conjunction with the “cracking a turned-off computer” of the previous section, (b) The two approaches we followed may have many false positives; thus, further time will be needed to verify if the identified strings are real passwords.

Countermeasures: In order to make their systems less vulnerable against the described attacks the users : (a) should consider the encryption of their hard disks, to provide maximum security for each file on the disk, with a password/PIN, (b) should avoid store their passwords in a plaintext file such as .docx, .txt etc; instead, users are advised to use a password manager that encrypts passwords with an encryption key (known as master key, generated by a master password from the user in most cases) since, in that case, stored passwords can only be accessed after inserting the master password. Moreover, if the users want to store passwords in files they should do so only in the files which are stored on external encrypted hard disks. Another effective countermeasure is to write in the file, not the passwords themselves, but instead words or sentences that can help the user to recall the passwords.

V. PLAINTEXT COPY: RECOVERY OF UNENCRYPTED COPIES OF DELETED DATA

Scenario: In this scenario, user transfers files of .txt, .docx, .pdf, .jpg type to an encrypted external drive to increase the security and prevent unauthorized users from accessing the files. So, our attacks aims at identifying an unencrypted copy of these transferred files.

Workaround: If there is access to the turned-on computer, it is possible to locate unencrypted copies of the transferred files.

Methods and tools: There are three different approaches for finding unencrypted copies of encrypted files: recovery from a shadow copy, recovery from the external disk based on the File History and recovery from OneDrive’s Recycle bin.

Fig 8 Files found utilizing File Explorer with keywords

```
C:\Users\syrgi>Password Searcher>python PasswordSearcher.py -p C:\Users\syrgi\Documents --min-pass 8 --max-pass 20 --pas s-complex 8 --line-password-regex 4
```


Fig 9 Files and passwords found utilizing PasswordSearcher

A. Shadow Copy Implementation and Prerequisites

Shadow Copy Implementation: In the case of Shadow Copy, we access the stored shadow copies of Windows 10 with ShadowCopyView [24]. A Shadow Copy (or Volume Shadow Copy/Snapshot Service) is a backup copy (or snapshot) of several computer files/volumes at a specific time. Shadow Copy stores the differences between the files in their current state and the initial files, as they are maintained in the backup, so as to minimize the required space. Moreover, in order to save backup space, Shadow Copy stores the system files of the computer and only small user files (some KBs of data the titles and the file properties are stored normally for every user file) unless the user has inserted a specific variable in the Registry Editor, which we will analyze below.

Snapshot Name	Explorer Path	Volume Path	Volume Name
\\.\GLOBALROOT\Device\HarddiskVolumeShadowCopy1	\\localhost.CS:\@GMT-2021-10-05-11:59:31	C:\	\\.\Volume{cfc3c186-0...
\\.\GLOBALROOT\Device\HarddiskVolumeShadowCopy2	\\localhost.CS:\@GMT-2021-10-05-12:07:39	C:\	\\.\Volume{cfc3c186-0...

Filename	Modified time	Created time	Entry Modified Time	File Size	Attributes	File Extension
stoisiea.pdf	10/5/2021 4:58:09 ...	10/5/2021 4:58:09 ...	10/5/2021 4:58:33 ...	40,074	A	pdf
profile-picture.jpg	10/5/2021 4:58:05 ...	10/5/2021 4:58:04 ...	10/5/2021 4:58:05 ...	444,738	A	jpg
passes.docx	10/5/2021 4:54:03 ...	10/5/2021 4:52:28 ...	10/5/2021 4:54:03 ...	12,395	A	docx
Microsoft Edge.lnk	10/5/2021 3:48:18 ...	10/5/2021 3:48:18 ...	10/5/2021 3:48:18 ...	1,446	A	lnk
desktop	10/5/2021 3:41:16 ...	10/5/2021 3:41:16 ...	10/5/2021 3:41:16 ...	282	AHS	no
creditcard.txt	10/5/2021 4:52:16 ...	10/5/2021 4:48:57 ...	10/5/2021 4:52:16 ...	29	A	txt
VSS	10/5/2021 4:50:27 ...	10/5/2021 4:50:21 ...	10/5/2021 4:50:28 ...			DI

Figure 7.39 VSS: To npuro Shadow Copy

Fig 10 Recovered files from Shadow Copies utilizing ShadowCopyView

Fig 11 Recovered files from external drive of File History

Shadow Copy Service can be triggered either by the user manually through a special Windows application or by Windows Update. Shadow Copies can be accessed not only

by ShadowCopyView, but also using two pre-installed Windows tools (i.e mklint [25] and vssadmin [26]) or by taking a raw disk image of the physical drive (e.g. using FTK Imager [27]) and analyzing it for shadow copies with libvshadows [28]. Using ShadowCopyView, we can find several versions of .txt, .docx, .pdf, .jpg in a Shadow Copy. Unfortunately, only .txt, .pdf files can be fully recovered, the rest are corrupted files with null bytes as shown in Figure 10. All files are recoverable only if the user had created a variable named ScopeSnapshot [29] with a value of 0 in the Registry Editor in "Computer\HKEY_LOCAL_MACHINE\SOFTWARE\WindowsNT\CurrentVersion\SystemRestore".

Prerequisites Shadow Copy: The prerequisites for effectively applying the listed encryption bypassing technique are : (a) computer must be turned on (or else the "cracking of a turned off computer technique" listed above should be applied first), (b) it is inherently probabilistic which files are recoverable as it is very unlikely for an average user to have set up the specified variable in the Registry Editor of Windows and (c) A version of the searched file should be stored on the computer's hard disk, when the shadow copy is created.

B. File History Implementation and prerequisites

File History Implementation: As for the file history the user must have enabled it on the "Back Up Settings" when initially setting up the backup software to an external drive (which is very likely). The "File history" application keeps backups of the most common folders (and their subfolders) of Windows 10 by default. Moreover, it allows the user to modify which files he/she wants to back up. Additionally, "File History" keeps backups of the changed files every hour by default, which can also be changed by the user. Lastly, "File history" allows the user to choose how long the backup will last with the default option to be "Forever". Obviously, for "File history" to work the external drive must be mounted. In the case of accessing the external drive where the File History is backed up we can retrieve all types of files (e.g. .txt, .pdf, .jpg, .docx etc) as shown in Figure 11.

Prerequisites File History: The prerequisites for effectively applying the listed encryption bypassing technique are : (a) computer must be turned on (or else the "cracking of a turned off computer technique" listed above should be applied first), (b) user must have enabled the "File History" software, (c) access to the external drive which is used by "File History" is required, (d) a version of the files containing useful information must be stored on the main hard disk of the computer when "File History" creates the backup.

C. OneDrive Implementation and prerequisites

OneDrive Implementation: In this case, the user has allowed OneDrive to keep backup copies of certain folders through her/his Microsoft account. OneDrive can keep backups of the most common folders (e.g. Desktop, Documents, Pictures) and their subfolders. OneDrive keeps a live backup of these folders if the computer is connected to the internet. In the event of a transfer of a file that is stored on these folders, the file is stored for 30 days in Recycle bin of onedrive.live.com and can be deleted only manually. Recycle bin can be accessed either by logging

into onedrive.live.com with user account or by logging in directly from the user's computer (instant login without password prompt) to the same site. In the case of accessing the recycle bin of onedrive.live.com we can retrieve all types of files (e.g. .txt, .pdf, .jpg, .docx etc) as shown in Figure 12.

Prerequisites OneDrive: The prerequisites for effectively applying the listed encryption bypassing technique are (a) computer must be turned on (or else the "cracking of a turned off computer technique" listed above should be applied first), (b) user must have enabled the option of backup in OneDrive, (c) The computer must be logged-in to the Microsoft account (which in most cases is automatic when the computer is turned on) and (d) an internet connection is required while the file is in a backup folder.

D. Lessons learned and Countermeasures

Lessons Learned: (a) From a shadow copy only small user files (with a size less than 100KB) can be recovered. (b) The "File History" and "OneDrive" based methods are based mostly on the carelessness and/or the limited technology experience of the user, (c) The user must have enabled the backup options via "File History" and "OneDrive" which an average user may not do.

Countermeasures: In order to make their systems less vulnerable against the described attacks the users : (a) should consider the encryption of their hard disks, to provide maximum security for each file on the disk. (b) When using "File History" users should consider encrypting the external drive they are using with a disk encryption software (BitLocker, VeraCrypt etc.). (c) When using OneDrive, users should store critical files through "Personal Vault" which requires another password in order to be accessed, locks after a certain time (e.g. 20 mins is the default lock time) and it does not keep deleted files in the One Drive Recycle bin.

Fig 12 Recovered files from Recycle bin of OneDrive.live

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work we analyze different scenarios of encryption workaround based on publicly available, as well as developed by us, solely open-source tools, and methods. The main conclusion emerged is that bypassing of the encryption is not trivial as it is based mainly on the observance of certain conditions or the choices of the user of the attacked system. So the effectiveness of each method is based on certain prerequisites. On the other hand, using encryption does not ensure the invincibility of the system. The approaches we followed bypassed encryption efficiently when certain conditions are met. Obviously, these conditions cannot be identified from the beginning, so certain research is required, before the implementation of the encryption bypassing techniques, so as to find if/which conditions can be efficiently applied.

Future work includes an expansion of these implementations techniques so as to be applied to : (a) more operational systems (i.e. Linux, MacOS) (b) mobile phones running various of those operational systems (i.e. Android and iOS), (c) additional disk encryption software (i.e. IBM-Guardium, Apple FileVault etc.), (d) additional Web Browsers (i.e. Microsoft Edge, Opera). We plan also to develop new techniques for finding deleted (transferred) files.

The main high-level goal of our work is to produce a guide for making citizens' systems more secure; this guide is planned to be given to the citizens as part of a software application coming from their public/city authorities and aiming at reducing the air pollution in cities, so as to make them feeling more comfortable when installing and using the underlying application.

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